

CHARACTERISTICS AND CHARACTERISTICS OF POULTRY AUDIT AND PRODUCTION COST INDICATORS

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<https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7812788>

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 31th March 2023

Accepted: 09th April 2023

Online: 10th April 2023

KEY WORDS

Audit, internal audit, expenses, cost, direct expenses, cost curves, production, profit, net income.

ABSTRACT

The article fully covers the classification and description as an object of audit of indicators of poultry costs and production costs.

Login. The main tool for obtaining reliable data on the financial condition of poultry farms in the context of agricultural modernization is audit. This will speed up the technical and technological renewal of poultry farms and expand their scale.

The report of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev at an expanded meeting of the Cabinet of Ministers dedicated to the results of the socio-economic development of the country in 2016 and the most important priority areas of the economic program for 2017 says: "Critical analysis, strict discipline and personal responsibility should be the daily rule of activity of each leader" established tasks require directly bringing the system of financial reporting and statistics in line with international standards.

This means that it is advisable for employees of this area in full compliance with international standards to provide a classification and description as an object of audit of indicators of poultry costs and production costs:

Degree of knowledge of the topic. Theoretical and practical aspects of calculation of production costs and cost of production in Uzbekistan Azlarov D.H., Bobozhanov O., Dzhumaniozov K.B., Urazov K.B., Tulakhodzhaeva MM, Dasmuratov R.H., Pardaev A.H., Researches by Toshnazarov S.H N., Musaev H.N., Ilkhomov S.I., Khasanov B.A. and others

Research methodology. This article uses analysis and synthesis of scientific knowledge, induction and deduction, a systematic approach, statistical and financial analysis, as well as economic and mathematical methods.

Main part. When considering complex issues of auditing production costs in poultry farms, it becomes necessary to define the general provisions of the economic essence of competition as an economic and legal category.

When carrying out production activities in any poultry farms, wages are naturally paid to employees, a one-time social payment, depreciation and other expenses. With the help of the circulation process, these expenses are always covered by income (income) received by

farms from the sale of poultry products, which ensures the continuity of the production process.

To calculate all the amounts of expenses for burqa farms, you need to bring them into a single cache, that is, reflect them in money. This indicator is the price.

In accordance with the Regulations on the composition of expenses: the cost of poultry production in poultry farms is an estimate of the cost of natural resources, raw materials, materials, fuel, energy, fixed assets, labor resources and other expenses incurred in the production of poultry products.

Any poultry farms before starting their activities determine how much they receive. The profit of poultry farms will depend mainly on the cost of poultry products and the cost of their production. And the price of poultry products is determined on demand and offer. The market is influenced by pricing laws, in conditions of free competition, prices for a poultry farm cannot be higher or lower, depending on the mood of the producer or buyer - it will be equated automatically. Another thing is that these are costs that form the cost of poultry production. They depend on the amount of labor and material resources used, the state of the art, the organization of production and other factors, can increase or decrease.

The cost of production in poultry farms is understood as the cost of resources used in the process of production and production of poultry products. This definition identifies key terms such as cost, resources, manufacturing processes, work execution, and services.

The term "Tannarch" is relatively new, in the works of Rudanovsky A.P., Ter-Davydov M.P., appeared in 1912. Before it, "cost," "cost of production," "real value," "real price." These synonyms established that the desired word consists of two meanings:

1. Expenses incurred for the finished products of all burqas;
2. Individual expenses for poultry products.

Thus, the cost includes all expenses of poultry farms, which determine their size.

During the production of assets in poultry farms to the form of resources, assets as a result of their write-off as a resource are turned first into production costs, and then into finished poultry products. When selling finished poultry products, there is a change in the composition of resources (assets), since when selling goods, poultry enterprises are spent at the cost of their sale.

The main tasks of accounting for production costs in poultry farms include:

- ✓ timely and direct reflection of actual costs associated with the production of poultry products under the relevant items;
- ✓ Preparation of information on operational control over the used production resources and their comparison with the relevant norms, standards and estimates;
- ✓ Identification of reserves for reducing the cost of greenhouse products, prevention of inefficient costs and duty;
- ✓ Determination of the results of domestic economic production by the structural structures of poultry farms.

The calculation of production costs for the implementation of these tasks should be organized in compliance with the following principles:

- ✓ Comparison of expense accounting indicators with planned indicators;
- ✓ All reporting periods include production costs in the cost of production;

- ✓ Recording and grouping of expenses by types, elements and items of expenses of production departments, poultry fraud;
- ✓ Compliance of expense objects with calculation objects;
- ✓ Ensure that production costs of existing regulations and derogations are separately reflected;

Expanding the composition of costs for the cost of poultry production;

Bring the methodology and organization of cost accounting as close as possible to international standards.

Based on the presented tasks, the company must comply with one of the most important conditions, namely: clear implementation of production costs for certain types of products (works, services); comply with the accepted classification.

This classification is based on the following characters (Table 1):

No	Cost classification
1.	Responsibility Centers
2.	Cost centers
3.	Dependence of individual expenses on production volumes
4.	Process Relation
5.	Types of expenses
6.	Frequency of expenses
7.	Place in the manufacturing process
8.	Relation to taxation
9.	Usefulness

Table 1. Optimized classification of production costs

The cost of poultry production is the monetary component of the cost of these products, consisting of material, labor and other expenses.

The poultry trademark is one of the main indicators of production efficiency and shows poultry farms how much poultry production accounted for.

The cost indicator is used to determine selling prices, calculate the profitability of poultry products, and determine cost reduction reserves.

In a market economy, it is important to reduce the cost of poultry products, since in a competitive environment the demand for poultry products and not only its quality, but also its cost, which makes up the price component, is important.

One of the most important ways to reduce the cost of production is to improve the management and establishment of direct and timely accounting of expenses, as well as to organize strict control over the rational use of material, labor and financial resources, a comprehensive reduction in costs and non-production requirements.

The following basic principles are laid down in the organization of accounting for poultry production costs:

- grouping of accounting expenses by economic aspects and items, types of poultry products and subdivisions of the enterprise;
- the accepted method of accounting for the costs of poultry production and its cost calculation does not change during the year;

- coordination of the cost accounting objects with the objects of calculation of the cost of poultry production;
- direct inclusion of income and expenses in the reporting periods;
- distribution of expenses related to current production costs and capital investments.

In order to ensure uniform principles of formation of information on expenses for production and sale of poultry products, a general procedure has been established for determining the costs included by the state in the cost of poultry products, distribution of income and expenses to groups, their accounting, regardless of the type of activity of enterprises, form of ownership and departmental subordination.

To this end, the Regulation "On the composition of expenses for the production and sale of products (works, services) and the procedure for the formation of financial results" was developed, approved by Decree of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan of February 5, 1999 No. 54.

The Regulation defines the methodology for the formation of financial results, provides a list of expenses related to the financial and economic activities of an economic entity, as well as a list of income received as a result of the production and economic activities of the enterprise.

A reasonable organization of accounting for production costs in poultry farms requires a clear and reasonable classification of these costs.

Depending on the degree of dependence on the amount of poultry products produced in poultry farms, expenses are divided into two groups: variable and conditionally constant costs.

Changing costs are expenses proportional to the volume and dynamics of poultry production. These include expenses for raw materials and basic materials, for the remuneration of employees of the main production, deductions from this salary for social insurance, etc.

Poultry farms can have a complex consisting of one element (raw materials, wages, etc.) and several elements (one-stage), depending on the composition of production costs (total costs, period costs, etc.).

Poultry farming is an important branch of agriculture. The main task facing this industry is to provide the population with eggs, poultry products, as well as provide production enterprises with raw materials and materials received from poultry farming.

Conclusion. In poultry farms, production costs can be classified according to various characteristics, as in agricultural production. Thus, in terms of economic content, poultry expenditures are divided into the following groups:

- * material costs - all material costs for poultry production (furniture, medicines, sedimentary materials, fuel and other materials);
- * labor expenses - the main and additional salaries accrued to employees engaged in poultry production;
- * social insurance contributions - mandatory deduction to the Pension Fund from the accrued salary fund for employees engaged in poultry production;
- * depreciation - the amount of depreciation accrued on property, plant and equipment and intangible assets related to poultry production;

* other expenses - all auxiliary and generalizing expenses for poultry production.

The costs of poultry production according to the calculation substances are reflected in terms of the following substances:

1. Remuneration and social security contributions;
2. Em-hashak.
3. Medicinal products.
4. Drop-down materials.
5. Work and services.
6. Expenses for the maintenance of property, plant and equipment.
7. Production and management costs.
8. Insurance benefits.
9. Other expenses.

The article "Remuneration and social insurance contributions" takes into account the corresponding social insurance contributions accrued in relation to the remuneration of workers engaged in growing, caring, bird care, egg collection and other such work. These expenses are transferred directly to the corresponding birds and types of work on the basis of primary farms.

The article "Em-hashak" takes into account food spent on feeding birds.

The article "Medicines" takes into account the cost of medicines spent on bird care.

The article "Planting materials" includes the cost of material that falls under the bird in the places of storage of birds.

The article "Work and Services" reflects the costs of payment for production services provided to poultry farms by other enterprises and organizations.

The item "Expenses for the storage of fixed assets" includes expenses related to the storage and use of fixed assets used directly in production. These include the maintenance and use of these property, plant and equipment, depreciation and amortization expenses.

Expenses for the maintenance and use of property, plant and equipment include the remuneration of employees serving property, plant and equipment, social insurance, fuel and lubricants, auxiliary production, as well as services of foreign organizations and other expenses.

The corrective costs include, first of all, the costs of repair shops.

Depreciation expense is the depreciation charge on fixed assets. Depreciation is recorded on a monthly basis in a separate analytical account "Depreciation allocated to assets used in poultry." At the end of the year, the amount of depreciation of fixed assets will be distributed to groups of birds and types of work, which will be issued with a special code.

The current adjustment expenses recorded in the Production Support account are distributed in proportion to the depreciation amount.

The item "Expenses for the organization of production and management" reflects the generalizing costs of poultry production.

The article "Insurance payments" takes into account the costs of bird insurance.

The item "Other expenses" reflects expenses directly related to poultry production, but not included in the above items.

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